

Anti-aging potential of the endophyte *Paenibacillus nuruki* in a *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* lifespan model

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the potential of *Paenibacillus nuruki* AASFL403 extract (PBE) to extend the lifespan of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Sc). The chronological lifespan assay was performed on three Sc strains with different genetic characteristics. Continuous or acute (30 min) treatment with PBE was performed with concentrations in the range of 0.1–2 mg/mL, depending on the experiment. Continuous treatment of exponentially growing *S. cerevisiae* 551 with 2 mg/mL PBE resulted in an increased specific growth rate and decreased doubling time. No effect on lifespan was observed for stationary-phase cell suspensions (non-metabolically active cells). The lifespan of Sc Δsod was extended up to day 11, compared to day 7 for the parental strain, when acute treatment (30 min) was performed. Despite its limited impact on yeast lifespan, PBE may act as an adaptogen, activating cellular defense mechanisms. Further research may reveal the exact mechanism of action of PBE.

Keywords

Anti-aging, endophyte, *Paenibacillus nuruki*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

Introduction

The genus *Paenibacillus* comprises Gram-positive, endospore-forming, motile, rod-shaped bacteria that normally colonize soil, the rhizosphere, and internal plant tissues as facultative endophytes. Across both cultivated and wild plants, studies using cultivation methods and DNA-based sequencing approaches consistently identify *Paenibacillus* as one of the dominant endophytic taxa. These studies also frequently report *Bacillus* as a co-dominant genus. *Paenibacillus* strains contribute to nitrogen fixation and to the solubilization of phosphate and potassium. They also pro-

duce indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) deaminase (an enzyme that reduces plant stress by lowering ethylene levels), siderophores, and a range of hydrolytic enzymes, including cellulases, chitinases, and glucanases. These factors modify plant cell walls and help suppress pathogenic organisms. Together, these activities support both effective colonization of the plant and promotion of plant growth. Recent review articles describe *Paenibacillus* as a major group of plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB). They report consistent performance under both field and greenhouse conditions, particularly in cereals and horticultural

crops (Morales-Cedeño et al. 2021; Tariq et al. 2025). *Paenibacillus* demonstrated effects on biomass accumulation, nutrient utilization, and disease suppression in Fabaceae. Recent reviews published in 2024–2025 consolidate these findings and further emphasize the genus's adaptability across diverse environments and host taxa (Mametja et al. 2025; Kumar et al. 2025; Tariq et al. 2025). Ecologically, endophytic *Paenibacillus* strains colonize diverse plant tissues through chemotaxis, adhesion, secretion of cell wall-modifying enzymes, and tolerance to plant-associated stresses, enabling systemic persistence and promotion of plant growth without causing disease (Dobrzyński and Kulkova 2025). Endophytic *Paenibacillus* strains have been isolated from cereals (wheat, sorghum, and maize), Solanaceae (tobacco), cucurbits, oilseed crops, legumes, and numerous medicinal plants. Their effects are particularly pronounced under stress conditions, where they enhance drought and salinity tolerance through modulation of osmolytes and hormonal balance while reducing biotic stress via pathogen antagonism, defense activation, and secretion of enzymes and lipopeptides associated with plant growth promotion and biocontrol activity (Dobrzyński and Kulkova 2025; Kumar et al. 2025).

Paenibacillus nuruki belongs to a cluster of *Paenibacillus* species commonly associated with plants. Although organism-specific endophytic data remain limited in the published literature, its phylogenetic proximity suggests a capacity for an endophytic lifestyle and PGPB-like functions characteristic of related species. As in other *Paenibacillus* species, the production of antimicrobial metabolites and the ability to modulate plant signaling pathways associated with stress resilience are highly probable (Tariq et al. 2025). Within this broad framework, *Paenibacillus nuruki* (type strain TI45-13ar^T) was described in 2019 from “nuruk,” a traditional Korean fermentation starter, but it is currently not a validly published species. It is phylogenetically closely related to *P. kyungheensis*, *P. hordei*, and *P. nicotianae*. It has a genomic G+C content of approximately 39% and menaquinone MK-7 as the predominant respiratory quinone, consistent with the chemotaxonomic traits of the genus (Kim et al. 2019).

Endophytic representatives of the genus *Paenibacillus* are prolific producers of small bioactive molecules and enzymes that affect both microorganisms and the plant host. Among the best characterized are nonribosomal lipopeptides. Fusaricidins, cyclic depsipeptides originally described in *P. polymyxa*, exhibit strong antifungal activity by disrupting spore germination and hyphal membranes. Beyond direct toxicity, purified fusaricidin from *P. polymyxa* WLY78 activates salicylic acid-dependent defense signaling and significantly contributes to disease control in *planta*. Polymyxins, cationic lipopeptides produced by certain *Paenibacillus* species, target Gram-negative bacteria in the rhizosphere. These lipopeptides, together with secreted chitinases, β -1,3-glucanases, proteases, and cellulases, account for much of the robust biocontrol observed in greenhouse and field studies. Genomic analyses and literature reviews from 2019–2025 identify lipopeptides as cen-

tral determinants in biocontrol and plant–microbe interactions within the genus *Paenibacillus* (Beatty and Jensen 2002; Li and Chen 2019; Dobrzyński and Nazejblo 2024).

Despite the limited information available, the activity of these bacteria creates a basis for further research into their potential to modulate biological processes in eukaryotes.

Based on the vast biosynthetic and metabolic potential of *Paenibacillus* and its proven capacity for modulating the plant life cycle, it was hypothesized that an extract from *Paenibacillus nuruki* may modulate the lifespan of the model organism *Sc*.

The test system was chosen because it is a routinely used model as a starting point in studies on aging, and it can provide preliminary information concerning some of the molecular pathways involved due to the presence of homologs and orthologs to human genes (Yalcin and Lee 2019; Kavilasha and Sasidharan 2021; Alugoju and Tencomnao 2024; Xu et al. 2026). Moreover, the results could be obtained within 2 weeks, making it suitable for rapid screening of anti-aging compounds compared to other model systems (Xu et al. 2026).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the potential of *Paenibacillus* extract (PBE) to extend the lifespan of *Sc*.

Materials and methods

Extract preparation

Bacterial cells from a single, previously isolated and identified pure colony of *Paenibacillus nuruki* AASFL403 were transferred into a sterile liquid medium consisting of double-strength yeast extract–tryptone (2× YT, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) (Zarev et al. 2025). Cultivation was carried out in Erlenmeyer flasks (250 mL total volume; 50 mL working volume) at 27 °C with shaking at 120 rpm for 48 h. Bacterial cells were harvested by centrifugation (4,000 rpm, 10 min), and the resulting supernatant was lyophilized to obtain the endophytic bacterial extract, rich in its metabolites (PBE). For the purposes of the study, a concentrated stock solution of PBE was prepared by dissolving 100 mg in 10 mL of sterile water (10 mg/mL). The solution was sterilized by filtration through a 0.22 μ m membrane filter under aseptic conditions, and solutions with specific concentrations were prepared.

Sc strains and cultivation conditions

Three strains of *S. cerevisiae* were used:

- 551—genotype MATa, *ura3*, *his3 Δ 200*:TymHis3AI, *sec53*—this strain is characterized by increased permeability of the cell wall due to the inserted *sec53* mutation (Pesheva et al. 2005).
- BY4741—genotype MATa; *his3 Δ 1*; *leu2 Δ 0*; *met15 Δ 0*; *ura3 Δ 0*—parental strain.
- Y06913 (Δ *sod*)—genotype BY4741; MATa; *ura3 Δ 0*; *leu2 Δ 0*; *his3 Δ 1*; *met15 Δ 0*; YJR104c:kanMX4—this

strain is isogenic to BY4741 with a deletion in the *SOD1* gene encoding cytoplasmic Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase.

BY4741 and Y06913 were purchased from the Euroscarf collection.

Model organism cultivation

The strains were stored for extended periods in glycerol at -80°C . Before use, they were thawed and inoculated onto Petri dishes containing YEPD medium (1% yeast extract, 2% bacto peptone, 2% bacto agar, and 2% glucose, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The Petri dishes were incubated for 72 h. After the incubation period, a single yeast colony was inoculated into liquid YEPD and incubated for 24 h on an orbital shaker at 30°C and 200 rpm.

A working suspension for each strain was prepared prior to each experiment. All the strains were cultivated under standard conditions (30°C , 200 rpm) in rich liquid YEPD medium. Cell growth was determined by measuring optical density at 600 nm. The starting cell concentration for each experiment was 1×10^7 cells/mL.

Chronological lifespan (CLS) assay

Chronological aging experiments were performed in synthetic complete (SC) medium (0.17% yeast nitrogen base without amino acids and ammonium sulfate, 0.5% ammonium sulfate, 0.079% complete amino acid mix containing 20 mg/L adenine, uracil, tryptophan, histidine, arginine, and methionine; 30 mg/L tyrosine, isoleucine, and lysine; 50 mg/L phenylalanine; 60 mg/L leucine; 100 mg/L each of glutamic acid and aspartic acid; 150 mg/L valine; 200 mg/L threonine; and 400 mg/L serine). The concentration of the added glucose was 2% (Sherman 2002).

Three modifications were tested:

- Continuous treatment of an exponentially growing cell suspension of strain 551. This strain was chosen based on the phenotypic characteristics. The *sec53* mutation leads to increased cell wall permeability. This offers an advantage in research on yeast, overcoming the main obstacle—the thick cell wall, which may be impermeable to some substances (Stoycheva et al. 2012). The effect of 0.1, 1, and 2 mg/mL PBE was assessed. The procedure follows the protocol by Stepień et al. (2020). The exponentially grown yeast cultures were washed twice with SC, and the pellets were resuspended in 30 mL of SC containing PBE at the appropriate concentration. The cell suspensions were then cultivated at 30°C and 200 rpm for 8 days. Cell survival was monitored on days 3, 5, and 8 by plating three Petri dishes containing complete medium per sample and counting the colony-forming units (CFU).
- Continuous treatment of stationary cells of strains 551, BY4741, and Y06913 followed the methodology

described by Alugoju and Tencomnao (2024). Cell suspensions were grown until reaching the stationary phase (approximately 72 h). After that, PBE was added to some of the samples to a final concentration of 2 mg/mL, and the other samples were used as controls. This was considered the first age point, corresponding to 100% survival. At regular intervals during CLS, the optical density of the cell suspensions was measured at 600 nm. The experiments lasted 21 days. On the last day, the cells were photographed under an Olympus BX-51 light microscope (40 \times). Viability was determined by staining the microscopic samples with 0.01% methylene blue (Smart et al. 1999).

- Acute treatment of exponentially growing cell suspensions of strains BY4741 and Y06913. After reaching the exponential growth phase, cell suspensions of BY4741 and Y06913 were treated with 2 mg/mL PBE for 30 min under optimal conditions. After treatment, cells were washed twice and resuspended in SC medium. Afterward, they were incubated at 30°C and 200 rpm for 14 days. On days 7, 11, and 14, samples were taken and plated on SC-containing Petri dishes. The number of cells was counted.

Statistical analysis

The results were presented as mean values \pm SEM. Statistical analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism software. Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test, was used to analyze growth curves and chronological lifespan experiments. Data are from at least three independent experiments. The growth rate (μ) (h^{-1}) was calculated following the formula: $\mu = (N_t - N_0) / (t_n - t_0)$, where N represents the cell survival extracted from the fitted model, representing the rate at which the cell population increased over time. T_d , the doubling time (h), was calculated as $T_d = \ln(2) / \text{growth rate } (\mu)$. Statistical significance was analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Values represent the mean \pm SEM of six independent biological replicates.

Results and discussion

Preliminary data revealed that treatment with PBE at concentrations of 0.1–2 mg/mL did not exhibit cytotoxicity (data not shown). The effect of continuous treatment with various PBE concentrations on cell survival in strain 551 was evaluated. The growth curves for strain 551 were similar, with no statistically significant differences among the concentrations (Fig. 1).

The statistical analysis revealed that the only factor influencing the growth curves was days (77.87% of the total variation, $p < 0.0001$). Based on the growth curve data, the specific growth rate and doubling time were calculated (Table 1). The results concerning the growth rate revealed that, although similar, the increase was statistically

Figure 1. Growth curves of *Sc* strain 551 after continuous treatment with 0.1, 1, and 2 mg/mL PBE. Data are presented as mean values \pm SEM ($n = 6$). Statistical significance was analyzed using two-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Asterisks indicate statistical significance (ns, $p > 0.05$; ****, $p < 0.0001$).

Figure 2. Chronological lifespan experiments. Stationary cells of strains 551 (A), BY4741 (B), and Δsod (C); (D) Microscopic images of the strains on day 21; dead cells were colored with 0.01% methylene blue. Data are presented as mean values \pm SEM ($n = 4$). Statistical significance was analyzed using two-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Asterisks provide information on statistical significance (ns $p > 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Chronological lifespan after 30-min treatment with 2 mg/mL PBE. A. BY4741; B. Δsod . Data are presented as mean values \pm SEM ($n = 6$). Asterisks provide information on statistical significance (ns $p > 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$). Statistical significance was analyzed using two-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Asterisks provide information on statistical significance (ns $p > 0.05$; **** $p < 0.0001$).

significant. Treatment with 0.1 and 1 mg/mL PBE resulted in comparable effects. On the other hand, treatment with 2 mg/mL PBE was statistically significantly different from all treatments and the control (untreated cells).

Based on the other parameter—doubling time—the data presented in Table 1 showed that the most pronounced statistically significant effect was again observed for 2 mg/mL PBE. This concentration was used

Table 1. The growth rate (μ) (h^{-1}) and the doubling time (T_d) (h) of *S. cerevisiae* exponential cells grown for 8 days to the stationary phase with or without PBE.

	Specific growth rate (μ) (h^{-1})	Doubling time (T_d) (h)
Control	0.16 \pm 0.001	4.22 \pm 0.009
0.1 mg/mL PBE	0.17 \pm 0.004*	4.04 \pm 0.020****
1 mg/mL PBE	0.17 \pm 0.001*	4.14 \pm 0.010*
2 mg/mL PBE	0.19 \pm 0.002****	3.69 \pm 0.030****

Values represent the mean \pm SEM of six independent biological replicates. Statistical significance was analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Asterisks provide information on statistical significance ($p < 0.05$; **** $p < 0.0001$).

for further analysis. The potential of this extract to affect the chronological lifespan was evaluated. The experiments were performed on all the strains: 551, BY4741 (wild type), and Δsod . The results revealed that 2 mg/mL PBE did not influence the chronological lifespan of the stationary cells. The growth curves of the controls and the treated cells were similar (Fig. 2). No statistically significant differences were observed between the untreated cells and those incubated with the extract, and this was also confirmed microscopically (Fig. 2).

Based on these findings, the extract does not appear to affect the lifespan of metabolically inactive cells.

To further examine this, a modified experimental design was implemented in which cells were treated for 30 min, washed, and their survival monitored for up to 14 days post-treatment.

Results presented in Fig. 3 indicated differences in response depending on the genetic characteristics and time. Comparing the control levels of both strains, it was observed that Δsod exhibited limited growth compared to the parental strain, with a decline after day 7 (Fig. 3A, B). The results confirm the existing literature, which shows that yeast strains deficient in superoxide dismutase are characterized by decreased lifespan (Fabrizio and Longo 2007; Van Raamsdonk and Hekimi 2012). Interestingly, when a 30-min treatment with 2 mg/mL PBE was performed, a significant 1.6-fold increase in cell survival on day 11 was observed compared to the same day for strain BY4741. The reported data indicate that this treatment is sufficient to protect cells lacking cytoplasmic Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase and to increase their lifespan. Based on the difference in response depending on the type of treatment, it could be suggested that this type of treatment may activate defense mechanisms that extend lifespan, whereas chronic treatment has no effect. One possible explanation is the extract's antioxidant potential. It is well known that decreases in antioxidant systems and the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) are related to aging (Sunthonkun et al. 2019). Contradictory data exist concerning the potential of natural extracts to extend the lifespan of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains with deleted *SOD*. Some authors report no effect (Xiang et al. 2011; Alugoju et al. 2025). Additionally, some extracts revealed anti-aging properties through antioxidant activity (Stirpe et al. 2017; Yalcin and Lee 2019). Another possible explanation could be related to the cellular processes when Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase is missing. The lack of the enzyme leads

to the accumulation of copper in cells, which, in turn, may affect thiol-containing compounds (Karlström and Levine 1991; Wawryn et al. 2002) and result in DNA damage and cellular lethality. It is possible that some of the constituents in the extract tested may chelate copper ions and protect the cells from further damage. Additional experiments may provide a better explanation for the observed difference in the response depending on the type of treatment.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained, it may be concluded that although PBE does not exert a pronounced effect on the lifespan of *Sc*, it may function as an adaptogen by activating cellular defense mechanisms. This effect could be associated with the modulation of stress-response pathways, enhancement of antioxidant capacity, or induction of protective systems that improve cellular resilience under adverse conditions.

These findings suggest that the biological activity of PBE is not directly linked to lifespan extension but rather to the improvement of cellular resistance to stress-induced damage. In this context, PBE may contribute to maintaining cellular homeostasis and mitigating the effects of genotoxic agents.

Further research aimed at elucidating the precise molecular mechanisms underlying these effects, such as the involvement of specific signaling pathways, gene expression changes, and interactions with oxidative stress markers, would provide deeper insight into its mode of action. Such studies may help clarify the potential applications of PBE, particularly in the field of antigenotoxicity and the development of natural products with protective cellular effects.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Alujoju P, Tencomnao T (2024) Effect of levan polysaccharide on chronological aging in the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 266: 131307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.131307>
- Alujoju P, Suwanichaksem P, Senabunyarith A, Prasad A, Tencomnao T (2025) *In vivo* anti-aging effects of naringin, a bioflavonoid: insights from the budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as a model organism. *BioGerontology* 26: 155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10522-025-10295-y>
- Beatty PH, Jensen SE (2002) *Paenibacillus polymyxa* produces fusaricidin-type antifungal antibiotics active against *Leptosphaeria maculans*, the causative agent of blackleg disease of canola. *Canadian Journal of Microbiology* 48: 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.1139/w02-002>
- Dobrzyński J, Kulkova I (2025) *Paenibacillus peoriae*: current knowledge and agricultural biotechnology potential of a close relative of *P. polymyxa*. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 118: 120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-025-02135-3>
- Dobrzyński J, Nازیębło A (2024) *Paenibacillus* as a biocontrol agent for Fungal Phytopathogens: Is *P. polymyxa* the only one worth attention? *Microbial Ecology* 87: 134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-024-02450-8>
- Fabrizio P, Longo VD (2007) The chronological life span of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. In: Tollefsbol TO (Ed.) *Biological Aging*. Humana Press, Totowa, NJ, 89–95. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-59745-361-5_8
- Karlström AR, Levine RL (1991) Copper inhibits the protease from human immunodeficiency virus 1 by both cysteine-dependent and cysteine-independent mechanisms. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 88: 5552–5556. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.88.13.5552>
- Kavilasha V, Sasidharan S (2021) Antiaging activity of polyphenol rich *Calophyllum inophyllum* L. fruit extract in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* BY611 yeast cells. *Food Bioscience* 42: 101208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2021.101208>
- Kim S-J, Cho H, Ahn J-H, Weon H-Y, Joa J-H, Kim J-S, Kwon S-W (2019) *Paenibacillus nuruki* sp. nov., isolated from Nuruk, a Korean fermentation starter. *Journal of Microbiology* 57: 836–841. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12275-019-9118-3>
- Kumar A, Chauhan P, Kumar A, Pooja Mishra T, Padiyal A, Walia Y, Dhir S, Pandey AK (2025) Latest progress (2020–2024) in bacterial endophyte research with special reference to plant disease management: achievements and challenges. *Discover Plants* 2: 234. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44372-025-00303-3>
- Li Y, Chen S (2019) Fusaricidin Produced by *Paenibacillus polymyxa* WLY78 induces systemic resistance against fusarium wilt of cucumber. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20: 5240. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20205240>
- Mametja NM, Ramadwa TE, Managa M, Masebe TM (2025) Recent advances and developments in bacterial endophyte identification and application: a 20-year landscape review. *Plants* 14: 2506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants14162506>
- Morales-Cedeño LR, Orozco-Mosqueda MaDC, Loeza-Lara PD, Parra-Cota FI, De Los Santos-Villalobos S, Santoyo G (2021) Plant growth-promoting bacterial endophytes as biocontrol agents of pre- and post-harvest diseases: fundamentals, methods of application and future perspectives. *Microbiological Research* 242: 126612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2020.126612>
- Pesheva M, Krastanova O, Staleva L, Dentcheva V, Hadzhitodorov M, Venkov P (2005) The Ty1 transposition assay: a new short-term test for detection of carcinogens. *Journal of Microbiological Methods* 61: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2004.10.001>
- Sherman F (2002) Getting started with yeast. *Methods in enzymology* 350: 3–41. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879\(02\)50954-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879(02)50954-X)
- Smart KA, Chambers KM, Lambert I, Jenkins C, Smart CA (1999) Use of methylene violet staining procedures to determine yeast viability and vitality. *Journal of the American Society of Brewing Chemists* 57: 18–23. <https://doi.org/10.1094/ASBCJ-57-0018>
- Stępień K, Wojdyła D, Nowak K, Mołoń M (2020) Impact of curcumin on replicative and chronological aging in the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast. *BioGerontology* 21: 109–123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10522-019-09846-x>
- Stirpe M, Palermo V, Bianchi MM, Silvestri R, Falcone C, Tenore G, Novellino E, Mazzoni C (2017) Annurca apple (*M. pumila* Miller cv Annurca) extracts act against stress and ageing in *S. cerevisiae* yeast cells. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 17: 200. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-017-1666-7>
- Stoycheva T, Pesheva M, Dimitrov M, Venkov P (2012) The Ty1 retrotransposition short-term test for selective detection of carcinogenic genotoxins. In: Pesheva M, Dimitrov M, Stefkova Stoycheva T (Eds) *Carcinogen*. InTech, Rijeka, Croatia. <https://doi.org/10.5772/38095>
- Sunthongkun P, Palajai R, Somboon P, Suan CL, Ungsurangri M, Soon-torngun N (2019) Life-span extension by pigmented rice bran in the model yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Scientific Reports* 9: 18061. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-54448-9>
- Tariq H, Subramanian S, Geitmann A, Smith DL (2025) *Bacillus* and *Paenibacillus* as plant growth-promoting bacteria in soybean

- and cannabis. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 16: 1529859. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2025.1529859>
- Van Raamsdonk JM, Hekimi S (2012) Superoxide dismutase is dispensable for normal animal lifespan. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109: 5785–5790. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1116158109>
- Wawryn J, Świącilo A, Bartosz G, Biliński T (2002) Effect of superoxide dismutase deficiency on the life span of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. An oxygen-independent role of Cu,Zn-superoxide dismutase. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) – General Subjects* 1570(3): 199–202. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4165\(02\)00197-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4165(02)00197-6)
- Xiang L, Sun K, Lu J, Weng Y, Taoka A, Sakagami Y, Qi J (2011) Anti-Aging effects of phloridzin, an apple polyphenol, on yeast *via* the SOD and Sir2 Genes. *Bioscience, Biotechnology, and Biochemistry* 75: 854–858. <https://doi.org/10.1271/bbb.100774>
- Xu P, Zhang X, Wang Y, Rahman SU, Huang D, Wu Z (2026) Yeast chronological lifespan model as a tool for screening aging interventions. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 27: 2633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms27062633>
- Yalcin G, Lee C-K (2019) Recent studies on anti-aging compounds with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as a model organism. *Translational Medicine of Aging* 3: 109–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tma.2019.10.001>
- Zarev Y, Enchev P, Ionkova I, Stoikov I, Donchev D, Ivanov IN (2025) Complete genome sequence of *Paenibacillus* spp. strain AASFL403 isolated from *Astracantha arnacanitha*. *Dunning Hotopp JC (Ed.). Microbiology Resource Announcements* 14: e00222-25. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mra.00222-25>